

Tentative Explanation of the Rotational Velocity Distribution in Galaxies

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Abstract

The lack of flattening of the rotational velocities of stars in a given spiral galaxy has been one of the greatest unsolved problems in astronomy. While the velocities of the planets of our solar system can be explained by a simple Kepler system, this does not appear to be the case when we examine the stars of a given galaxy. Looking at the planets in our solar system, we observe a decrease in rotational speed with increasing distance from the center, i.e., the Sun. Various hypotheses have been formulated to solve the problem of the missing decrease in the orbital velocity of a star as a function of its distance to the center of the respective galaxy.

Large quantities of dark matter (the so-called halos of dark matter) have been assumed to exist around the galaxy to explain the movements of stars in the galaxy while retaining Kepler's laws. A modification of the Newtonian force-acceleration relationship has also been postulated (known as the MOND hypothesis). Here, an alternative explanation is proposed based on the assumption that stars, in contrast to planets, represent electrically charged bodies rather than electrically uncharged bodies. This assumption can be used to explain the observed velocities of stars.

Keywords: rotational velocity distribution, galaxies, astronomy, stars

Résumé

L'absence d'aplatissement des vitesses de rotation des étoiles d'une galaxie spirale donnée demeure l'un des plus grands mystères non résolus à ce jour de l'astronomie.

Si les vitesses des planètes de notre système solaire peuvent être expliquées et correspondent à un simple système de Kepler, cela ne semble pas être le cas si nous examinons les étoiles d'une galaxie donnée. Lorsque nous observons les planètes de notre système solaire, nous constatons une baisse de la vitesse de rotation à mesure que la distance par rapport au centre, c'est-à-dire par rapport au soleil, augmente.

Diverses hypothèses ont été émises pour expliquer l'absence de baisse des vitesses de rotation des étoiles en fonction de l'éloignement par rapport au centre de la galaxie donnée.

On a, d'une part, supposé qu'il y avait de grandes quantités de matière noire à travers les galaxies (que l'on appelle les halos) qui expliquent les mouvements des étoiles dans la galaxie, tout en conservant les lois de Kepler dans cette approche. D'autre part, on a même postulé qu'il y avait une modification de la relation de Newton entre force et accélération (connues comme les hypothèses MOND). Une explication alternative est présentée ici: l'hypothèse selon laquelle les étoiles, contrairement aux planètes, ne constituent pas des corps électriquement neutres, mais des corps électriquement chargés. Cette hypothèse peut expliquer les vitesses constatées des étoiles.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rotation of galaxies was discovered in 1914 by Slipher when he detected inclined absorption lines within the nuclear spectra of the M31 and Sombrero galaxies. [1] Subsequently, in the same year, Wolf also discovered similar inclined lines for the atomic range of M81. [2] Following these discoveries, in 1918, Pease used the Mt. Wilson 60-inch telescope to investigate the rotation of the vast nebula in the Andromeda galaxy, showing that the rotation curves indicate how the velocities of objects in the galaxy change as a function of the object's distance from the center. [3] Observations of the Doppler shift in the star spectral lines of given galaxies have shown that galaxies do not rotate like a rigid body or like a gravitationally bound Kepler system. Typically, a Kepler distribution of the velocities of stars would be expected for a gravitationally bound system. The American scientist Vera Rubin reported the first investigations of this phenomenon in the 1970s. In fact, the rotation curves of many galaxies, including that of our Milky Way, can be described by a different explanation.

After an initial rise in the rotational velocities of the inner regions with increasing distance from the center, which corresponds to the rotation of a rigid body, the velocities become approximately constant in the middle and outer regions of the galaxy. In fact, inhomogeneities are observed in the rotational velocities, although

these inhomogeneities are wave-like patterns and not Keplerian. For larger distances from the center (radii), the velocities are nearly constant.

2. THE NATURE OF THE PROBLEM

To explain the observed phenomenon of the missing flattening of the rotation curves, various explanatory models have been proposed.

On the one hand, the existence of large quantities of black matter has been assumed to explain the movements of the galaxies while adhering to Kepler's laws. This is currently the most popular explanation included in most physics and astronomy textbooks.

On the other hand, a modification of the Newtonian force-acceleration relationship has been postulated, called the MOND hypothesis (modified Newtonian dynamics, Milgrom Hypotheses [4,5]). However, to date, it has not been possible to experimentally detect differences between the acceleration of electrically neutral bodies and those that follow the Newtonian law. Neither explanation has yet been proven.

3. FUNDAMENTAL HYPOTHESIS

It is assumed here that a star is an electrically charged body. A star is extremely hot and has atomic nuclear fusion processes occurring inside and even on the surface of a given star. In these nuclear reactions, many particles are released. Many of the elements formed in the interior of stars are radioactive and emit particle radiation.

To this extent, we must assume that a star not only emits light but also emits a great variety of particle radiation. This radiation primarily takes the form of beta rays, i.e., electrons, emitted by a given star. For this reason, we must assume that stars emit electrons, at least at the beginning of their lives.

The electrons emitted from most stars are presumably accelerated toward the active galactic nucleus, which is believed to be a black hole in almost all cases. If so, the electrons from the outer stars accelerate across the middle stars toward the inner stars of a galaxy until they are finally absorbed by the active galactic nucleus.

Classically, to calculate the orbital velocity of a planet, Newton's law of gravitation is equated with the centrifugal force. In this case, the mass of the planet cancels out. For stars, the charge of the star has also to be taken into account. Charge does not cancel out in contrast to the mass of a planet. The charge causes an additional attractive force. Consequently, in order to achieve a stable orbit, a higher line speed and a higher centrifugal force are required

4. THEORY

Newton's law was founded to explain the motion of the planets around the Sun. Analogously, the electrostatic Coulomb law was developed to describe the motion of electrons. There is no reason why these two laws cannot be combined.

Moreover, there is no reason why there should not be an intermediate force between mass and charge, which is called the mass-charge force herein. This mass-charge force has already been described by the author in several previous publications [e.g., 6].

Both the Newtonian gravitational law and the Coulombic electrostatic law can be combined into a single law:

$$(1) \quad F = \gamma(m_1 + bq_1)(m_2 + bq_2) / r^2$$

Combined force from Coulombic electrostatic law and Newtonian gravitational law.

m_1 : mass of body 1; m_2 : mass of body 2; F : resulting force; γ : gravitational constant; b -constant: 11×10^9 kg/C; q_1 : charge of body 1; q_2 : charge of body 2; and r : distance between the two bodies. This new force includes an additional intermediate force between mass and charge.

Thus far, the implications of such an intermediate force have been explained by the phenomenon of influence. This intermediate force is assumed here to explain the

movement of stars around the galactic center and is taken as the main driving force for maintaining the orbit of stars around the galactic center.

The movements of stars are primarily determined by the force of attraction acting between the charge on the stars and the mass of the galactic center.

Since the intermediate mass-charge force is orders of magnitude greater than the gravitational force, the mass-charge force should be the main driving force responsible for the observed movements of stars in galaxies. For this reason, the movement of the stars around the galactic center is much faster than would be the case according to the Keplerian distribution only.

In the case of young galaxies, one can expect the stars to be continuously charged since more electrons than protons leave the star per unit time. This case should result in a continuous electron flow within the disk of stars in a galaxy. This electron flow will be directed from the outer stars toward the galactic center, flowing across the inner stars. Therefore, the middle and inner stars experience both an electron inflow and an electron outflow. Consequently, the stars of a galaxy have a greater charge as one moves outward from the center of a galaxy. The charge of a star is thus proportional to its distance from the galactic center. This relationship is expected to break down in the case of old galaxies.

At some instance in time, the stars of a galaxy will reach a maximum charge. The electron flow then comes to a stop, resulting in a Keplerian distribution of velocities.

The consequences of this constant electron flow in a newly formed galaxy with an active galactic nucleus are described below.

The inner stars of a given galaxy should be relatively electrically neutral because of the electron flow. For these inner stars, there is an influx and outflux of electrons. This situation is completely different for the outer stars of a galaxy. Although the outer stars also have an efflux of electrons, there is no influx of electrons. As a result, the stars in the periphery of the galaxy have an increasingly higher charge. The charge q of a star should be proportional to its distance (or radius) from the center ($q \sim r$).

$$(2) \quad q \sim r \text{ and } q = k \cdot r$$

Proposed proportionality between distance of a star from the galactic center and charge of this star. r : distance q : electrostatic charge, k : proportionality constant

As a result, the electrical charge of a given star will increase moving away from the galactic center ($q \sim r$) and ($q = kr$). We now assume that not only mass but also mass and electric charge are equally important to describe the attractive force acting on a given star within a galaxy. Therefore, it is clear that the force of attraction acting on a star within a galaxy becomes larger with increasing distance from the galactic center. This attractive force is relevant for the orbit of a star around the central black hole. To compensate for the strong attractive force, the orbital velocity of the star must remain high. The velocity distribution cannot flatten out, which contrasts that expected for a Keplerian system of electrically neutral bodies, such as planets.

Stars located further out in a galaxy experience a stronger attractive force toward the central black hole because they are more electrically charged. To compensate for this stronger force of attraction, they must then move with a higher orbital velocity. If we assume that the electric charge of a star increases proportionally with the distance (or radius r) from the galactic center, then we obtain a velocity distribution equal to the experimentally observed distribution. There should be no dependency of the velocity on the radius r , and the radius r should drop out of all relevant equations. After the attractive centripetal force and centrifugal force are equalized, the resulting equation no longer depends on the radius r at large radii. Therefore, stars in stable orbits around the galactic center are acted upon by balanced centripetal and centrifugal forces. All stars with an unbalanced electrical charge that are unable to support a stable orbit will either fall into the galactic center (for example, if the electric charge is too high) or drift out and away from the galaxy into the universe (similar to neutral stars or when the charge of a peripheral star becomes too low).

The observed rotational velocities of stars around the galactic center can be explained without the assumption of dark matter or dark energy; it is also not necessary to modify Newton's law. The observed matter alone is sufficient to describe the velocity distribution. To experimentally confirm the model described here, it would be helpful to develop new technologies that can investigate the charge distribution in galaxies. It would be interesting to visualize a galaxy's beta rays via electron telescopes and by generating images of galaxies that reflect their electron emissions. Radio-astronomy would also be helpful in this regard.

Such an electron telescope should ideally be positioned in orbit around the earth. Thus, it might be possible to verify whether the outer stars of a newly formed galaxy

actually emit more electrons (with a stronger beta spectrum) than the inner stars. Ideally, when observing a newly formed galaxy with an active galactic center, a continuous decrease in electron luminosity of the stars should be revealed, with the luminosity continuously decreasing moving inward.

Older Galaxies

While the stars of younger galaxies are expected to become increasingly more electrically charged in the described manner, the charge states of stars in older galaxies should no longer change and should be stable. For this reason, only the stars belonging to younger galaxies should emit electrons (or beta rays) as described above. The beta ray intensity of stars in younger galaxies should be higher for stars that are more distant from the edge of the galactic disk.

Eventually, an equilibrium emerges. At a certain point, the stars of a given galaxy are so strongly charged that electrons can no longer overcome the electrostatic potential. In this second phase, the charge state of the stars of that galaxy is stabilized. The charge of these stars “freezes”, and these stars no longer radiate within the beta spectrum.

Nevertheless, the charge state of the stars of such a galaxy can still be recognized based on the diffraction patterns for particle radiation passing through the galaxy and by the examination of radio waves. As a result of these processes, in older galaxies, the outer stars should have a stronger electrical charge than the inner stars. This expectation provides a possible method to experimentally prove the theory described

herein. This hypothesis may also explain the different radio-astronomical images obtained for galaxies such as Andromeda (radiation halo at the outer circle) and NGC6946, where the particle and radiation flows appear to be directed toward the center (galaxies with an active galactic nucleus).

Equations

The following equations result from an equalization of the centrifugal force and the mass-charge binding force of a star toward the central black hole.

$$(3) \quad \frac{m_s v^2}{r} = \gamma \frac{(m_s + b q_s) m_{CN}}{r^2}$$

$$(4) \quad v = \sqrt{\gamma \frac{(m_s + b q_s) m_{CN}}{m_s r}}$$

$$(5) \quad v = \sqrt{\gamma \left(\frac{m_{CN}}{r} + \frac{b \cdot q_s \cdot m_{CN}}{m_s r} \right)} = \sqrt{\gamma \left(\frac{m_{CN}}{r} + \frac{b \cdot k \cdot m_{CN}}{m_s} \right)}$$

$$(6) \quad v = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma m_{CN}}{r} \left(1 + \frac{b q_s}{m_s} \right)}$$

Regarding the equations, the centrifugal force of a given star is equalized to the mass-charge force between the galactic center and the star. m_s : mass of the star; v : velocity of the star; r : distance of the star to the center; m_{CN} : mass of the galactic

center/central nuclei; q_s : charge of the star; γ : gravitational constant; and b-constant: $11 \times 10^9 \text{ kg/C}$.

Furthermore, k is the constant in the relation $k \cdot r = q$, with

$k = 10 \text{ C/kpc}$ for $r > 0$ and $r < 10 \text{ kpc}$ and

$k = 10^{20} \text{ C/kpc}$ for $r > 10 \text{ kpc}$.

Thus, k is thought to be different for the relative neutral stars near the galactic center ($k = 10 \text{ C/kpc}$) and high for charged stars far beyond the galactic center ($k = 10^{20} \text{ C/kpc}$). kpc represents kilo-parsec distance from the center.

These different constants result from an electrostatic neutralization of the inner stars nearest the galactic center. For the distant stars, this neutralization is missing.

To give two examples for the Sun, these equations will result in no changes due to the short distance between the Sun and the galactic center.

$$(7) \quad v = \sqrt{\gamma \left(\frac{\left(1m_{sun} + 10^{10} \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{C}} 10 \frac{\text{C}}{\text{kpc}} 8\text{kpc} \right) \cdot m_{CN}}{m_{sun} 8\text{kpc}} \right)} \Rightarrow m_{sun} = 10^{30} \text{ kg} \gg bq = bkr = 10^{11} \text{ kg}$$

In this case, the charge-associated acceleration is very small compared to the mass-associated acceleration. However, for a star far away ($r = 100 \text{ kpc}$) from the galactic center, the following holds:

$$(8) \quad v = \sqrt{\gamma \left(\frac{\left(1m_{star} + 10^{10} \frac{kg}{C} 10^{20} \frac{C}{kpc} 100kpc \right) \cdot m_{CN}}{m_{star} 100kpc} \right)} \Rightarrow m_{star} = 10^{30} \text{ kg} \ll bq = bkr = 10^{32} \text{ kg}$$

Thus, for a star far away from the galactic center, the charge-associated acceleration becomes more important than the mass-associated acceleration.

A comparison to the Milgrom Hypotheses/MOND theory shows that both yield similar results. By comparing the equations, one arrives at the following result:

$$(9) \quad \text{Milgrom Hypotheses: } F = \mu \cdot m \cdot a = \mu \cdot \frac{v^2}{r} m \quad \text{with} \quad \mu = \frac{a}{a_0}$$

F: Force, μ : Milgrom- factor, m: mass, a. acceleration, v: velocity, r: distance.

Thus, the Milgrom introduces an additional acceleration into his equations.

This corresponds to the equations given here as follows:

$$(10) \quad \frac{1}{\mu} = \left(1 + \frac{bq}{m_s} \right) = \left(1 + \frac{bkr}{m_s} \right)$$

μ : Milgrom- factor, m_s : mass of a star, b: b-constant, q: charge, k: constant, r: distance

An additional acceleration is introduced into the equations. However, the additional acceleration results from the mass-charge interaction between the charge of the stars and the mass of the galactic center. This becomes important when the charge-associated acceleration becomes equal to or larger than the associated acceleration, which occurs at greater distances from the galactic center.

5. CONCLUSIONS

New observations recently published in *Nature* [7,8] show that the velocity distributions in older galaxies differ from the velocity distributions in younger galaxies. In particular, a Keplerian distribution has been found for older galaxies [7,8]. The model described herein is consistent with this new finding. Because the stars in older galaxies are maximally charged, the electron flux ceases. As a result, no charge compensation can occur for stars in such galaxies. The proportionality between charge and radius is no longer maintained. Therefore, a Keplerian velocity distribution will follow.

6. PROVING THE HYPOTHESES

According to the hypothesis, the outermost stars should not be within the electron-flux zone of the galaxy. However, all stars lying inside this region should be within the electron-flux zone. This electron flux increases further inward and increasingly neutralizes the charges of the stars. The formation of spiral arms follows from this

notion. Furthermore, different zones with different movements follow. A neutral environment with Keplerian motion occurs in the interior of a galaxy. In the outer parts, a linear charge gradient with constant velocities occurs.

However, according to the theory presented in this study, there should be not only a circular movement of the stars around the galactic center but also additional overlaying movements of the stars, which should result in a complex differential motion pattern of the stars in the arms of a spiral galaxy. For a star with an orbital velocity that is too high, it should move outward from the arm of a spiral galaxy to its surface. This star is then no longer within the "protective" electron-flux zone of the galaxy. As a result, this star should become increasingly electrically charged. Because the cooling effect and the neutralizing effect of the electron flux is now absent, the star should shine brighter during this charging phase.

However, when the star becomes increasingly electrically charged, the attracting force acting toward the galactic center also begins to increase. As a result, this star is now attracted and should move toward the galactic center, and at some point, its position will shift behind the other stars, making it no longer the outermost star. Other stars now become the outermost stars. Our star is now back in the electron-flux zone of the galaxy, and the star is now increasingly electrically discharged. The star should not emit as much light due to the decreasing charge of this star and decreasing attraction force, which acts toward the galactic center. However, because the star continues to have a very high orbital speed, it slowly moves outward again due to centrifugal force.

The differential dynamics and movements of the stars in the arms of a spiral galaxy

are therefore quite complex and characterized by a non-constant attraction force toward the center, which is better described by an undulating increasing and decreasing attraction force toward the center. In this way, the hypothesis described herein could be tested experimentally.

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